

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BMS	Battery management system
BOS	Balance of plant
DOD	Depth of discharge
EOL	End of life
ESS	Energy storage system
EV	Electric vehicle
FAT	Factory acceptance testing
KPI	Key performance indicator
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
LCO	Lithium cobalt oxide
LCOS	Levelised cost of storage
LFP	Lithium iron phosphate
LIB	Lithium-ion battery
LMO	Lithium manganese oxide
LTO	Lithium titanate oxide
NCA	Lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide
NMC	Lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide
RFI	Request for information
RFP	Request for proposal
RFQ	Request for quotation
SAT	Site acceptance testing
SEI	Solid electrolyte interphase
SOC	State of charge
SOH	State of health

1 Introduction

Batteries play a key role in the ongoing energy transition, as they can be effectively used to provide short time energy storage to even out the disparity between the timing of renewable energy generation and load consumption. Lithium-ion battery (LIB) is the prevailing battery technology of choice for fast-acting storage, short-time power storage and short- and medium time energy storage due to their high performance, long lifespan, and affordable cost driven by the high volume production for electric vehicles (EVs) and electronics industry. However, even as the battery pack cost for EV industry has fallen rapidly and has already passed below 200 €/kWh mark for the industry leaders [1], [2], the cost of batteries for stationary applications is still in the area of 400–1500 €/kWh [3] [2]. The high variation is caused by the wide range of applications and the associated requirements for performance, safety, and lifespan.

The economics of battery storage is highly influenced by the lifespan in the application. It makes a big difference whether a battery can endure 3000 or 6000 cycles for almost similar purchase costs. Therefore, in many applications, the levelized cost of storage (LCOS) is a better economic indicator than the investment cost. Moreover, in early studies and comparison of storages, the cost per installed energy capacity per cycle (€/kWh/cycle) is a convenient indicator for fast evaluation. Nonetheless, the high cost of industrial batteries is still limiting their usage in many fields including distribution grid applications. It is therefore of utmost importance to first identify a viable business case using realistic estimates for battery price and lifespan, and only after that, to proceed with more detailed design, planning, and procurement.

The purpose of this document is to provide guidance for the procurement of battery storages for stationary grid applications. The document builds upon INVADE deliverables D6.1 *Storage system dimensioning and design tool* [4], D6.2 *Battery techno-economics tool* [5], and D6.4 *Advanced state of health diagnostics tool* [6]. The reader is referred to these reports for more background information and details on the topics addressed in this guide. Technological background is given only for LIBs, but the methodologies are generic in nature and can be applied for other battery technologies as well. Thorough guidelines and supplementary material for energy storage procurement can be found in [7], [8], [9].

2 Applications and use cases

There are many energy storage services and classifications. The classification based on EASE Position Paper on Maximising Social Welfare of Energy Storage Facilities through Multi-Service Business Cases [10] is shown in Figure 1. Descriptions and technical characteristics of some applications are presented in [11] and [9].

Generation/Bulk Services	Ancillary Services	Transmission Infrastructure Services	Distribution Infrastructure Services	Customer Energy Management Services
Arbitrage	Primary Frequency Control	Transmission Investment Deferral	Capacity Support	End-user Peak Shaving
Electric Supply Capacity	Secondary Frequency Control	Angular Stability	Contingency Grid Support	Time-of-use Energy Cost Management
Support to Conventional Generation	Tertiary Frequency Control	Transmission support	Distribution Investment Deferral	Particular Requirements in Power Quality
Ancillary Services RES Support	Load Following		Distribution Power Quality	Maximising self-production & self-consumption
Capacity Firming	Frequency Stability of Weak Grids		Dynamic, Local Voltage Control	Demand Charge Management
RES Curtailment Minimisation	Black Start		Intentional Islanding	Continuity of Energy Supply
Limitation of Upstream Perturbations	Voltage support		Limitation of Upstream Disturbances	Limitation of Upstream Disturbances
Seasonal Arbitrage	New ancillary services		Reactive Power Compensation	Compensation of the Reactive Power
Cross-Sectoral Storage				EV integration

Figure 1: Services provided by energy storage [10].

A battery storage can be used for one or multiple services. Multi-service business case allows revenue stacking from multiple services. In this document, individual services that a battery can provide are called applications, whereas multi-services business cases are called use cases. The use case, and therefore, the primary application or the mix of applications has a high impact on the choice of energy storage technology, as the duty cycles and required cycle life are heavily affected. The main requirements that need to be fulfilled in order to develop a multi-service business case are discussed in [10].

There is a wide range of storage technologies available for grid applications, ranging from huge storages such as pumped hydrostorages and compressed-air storages to medium-sized and small storages such as electrochemical storages. Figure 2 shows the applications of grid-connected energy storages segmented by discharge time. The main technologies of batteries for grid applications are lithium-ion (Li-ion), lead acid, nickel cadmium (NiCd), sodium sulphur (NaS), sodium nickel chloride (NaNiCl₂), and redox flow. Lithium-ion battery is a very fast-acting storage technology that can be used effectively for load durations from seconds up to several hours, and it is the prevailing

battery technology for fast-acting storage, short-time power storage and daily energy storage due to its high performance, long lifespan, and affordable cost.

Figure 2: Applications of grid-connected energy storages segmented by discharge time [12].

3 Lithium-ion battery technologies

Lithium based batteries have high cell potential due to the very low reduction potential. In addition, lithium is the third lightest element, which enables the high gravimetric and volumetric capacity. However, lithium is highly reactive, making it challenging to produce inherently safe batteries. So far, this issue has been overcome by not using metallic lithium, but instead using compounds that are capable of donating lithium ions. The main cathode materials currently are lithium cobalt oxide (LCO), lithium manganese oxide (LMO), lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC), lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide (NCA) and lithium iron phosphate (LFP). The most common anode material is currently graphite. A small percentage of batteries utilize lithium titanate oxide (LTO) anode.

The use of various different materials and electrode compositions results in batteries with a wide variety of characteristics. The current commercial LIBs have a specific energy in the range of 90–250 Wh/kg, NCA cathode having the highest specific energy and LFP the lowest [13]. The majority of commercial LIBs use carbon based anodes. The other commercial anode composition is LTO, which has a very long cycle life, high charge/discharge rate, and is very tolerant to temperature. However, the electrochemical potential of the half-cell is higher, which results in lower voltage of the full cell, and consequently, in lower energy density than carbon anodes. LTO also has higher cost per kWh. Therefore, LTO anode is typically combined with NMC cathode. LTO is most suited to applications where very high charging rates or very long cycle life is necessary.

A performance comparison and the main applications of different LIB technologies are shown in Figure 3. The stationary renewable energy storage market for electrical grid and residential applications is currently dominated by NMC and LFP technologies, which both offer affordable cost and long lifetime, and consequently, fairly low €/kWh/cycle metric. LTO technology is common in some specific highly demanding applications such as utility frequency regulation. The residential storage systems are typically designed and warranted for a lifetime of 10 years or more assuming one daily cycle, meaning a warranted cycle lifetime of more than 3500 cycles. The remaining capacity at the end-of-life varies between 60–80% of the rated capacity.

Figure 3: Comparison of different LIB technologies.

Stationary battery energy storage systems contain many subsystems that need to be taken into account in the application design and storage procurement. Figure 4 illustrates these subsystems and the associated cost and price structure of stationary battery storages. The storage system cost is dependent on the power capacity and the lifetime. The increasing power capacity increases the cost via three ways: (i) power-optimized battery cells and modules are more expensive than energy-optimized ones, (ii) the power conversion system (PCS) needs to be rated for higher power, and (iii) the balance of system (BOS) costs are higher because e.g. the thermal management system needs to be rated for higher heat generation. Especially the bigger PCS increases the cost of the system.

Figure 4: Illustrative system cost and price structure of stationary battery storage [2].

4 Storage procurement

The first step is to explore the feasibility of different applications and to define the use case of the storage. The actual design and planning phase can then be started, in which more detailed calculations and analysis are performed to assess and optimize the technical and economical aspects and to define the performance requirements for the storage. The main objectives are to validate the business case and to gather and document all requirements for the storage system that need to be fulfilled. When the preliminary requirement specification is completed, the actual procurement phase can be started. The requirement specification is needed in the tendering phase, in which a request for proposal (RFP) is issued to potential battery suppliers. The proposals are then evaluated with several criteria and indicators, and the final decision-making is performed based on the requirements, proposals, selection criteria, and indicators.

Figure 5 illustrates the typical procurement process for stationary grid-connected storages. The process has five main phases: (i) application design, (ii) permitting analysis, (iii) requirement analysis, (iv) tendering, and (v) decision-making. In the following, these phases will be described in more detail.

Figure 5: Typical procurement process of battery storages projects. The needed new inputs are shown above the phases, whereas the main outcomes are shown below the phases.

4.1 Application design

The primary application and the possible other applications are first defined based on a screening assessment. The battery usage profile is impacted by the use case and the associated services as well as the electric energy consumption and renewable generation profiles, the electricity price, and the tariff. A prerequisite for more detailed feasibility studies and requirement analysis is the determination of anticipated duty cycles¹. The actual battery load profiles can be estimated by simulating the system using e.g. mixed-integer linear programming or rule-based controls. The obtained battery duty cycles and their occurrences then constitute the basis for the determination of functional requirements². Feasibility studies, techno-economic optimization, and preliminary battery dimensioning can be performed using approximate budget price information of different battery technologies. The main outcomes of this phase are the use case definition, cost–benefit analysis, risk analysis, and the functional requirements.

The second ENTSO-E Guideline for Cost–Benefit Analysis of Grid Development Projects [8] was recently published by the European Commission. It is targeted for large projects and provides detailed guidelines including KPI definitions and calculation methods that can be applied also for battery energy storage projects.

¹ Terms *mission profile* and *load profile* are commonly used instead of *duty cycle*.

² Functional requirements include the essential operational performance requirements such as energy capacity, power capacity, efficiency, ramp rate, and power quality.

4.2 Permitting analysis

Energy storage system installations and integration into the built environment may need permits from the authorities. Therefore, all agencies and other entities that are involved in the review and final approval of the energy storage system (ESS) and its integration with the built environment shall be identified and contacted in the early stage of the planning to ensure smooth information exchange and to obtain the requirements regarding the rules, regulations, codes, and standards.

4.3 Requirement analysis

A battery requirements specification is needed when requesting proposals from the battery suppliers. This document should contain all necessary information for offering a battery storage solution. On the other hand, it should be technology neutral and open to different technology choices and system designs. Table 1 gathers typical categories and items that are covered in the requirement specification.

Table 1: Typical items included in the requirements specification.

Functional requirements	Non-functional requirements
<p>Performance: power, energy, voltage, current, roundtrip efficiency</p> <p>Conditions: ambient/operating temperatures, humidity</p> <p>Lifetime: number of load cycles, calendar lifetime, end-of-life criteria, design lifetime in the application</p> <p>Dynamics: response time, ramp rate</p> <p>Other: Self-discharge rate, power quality</p>	<p>Infrastructure: physical size and weight constraints, grid connection, thermal management, fire suppression</p> <p>Control: communication protocols, battery management system, energy management system, supervisory control and data acquisition, cyber security</p> <p>Lifecycle: delivery, installation, commissioning, training, maintenance, repair, decommissioning, recycling/disposal</p> <p>Warranty & support: warranty period and conditions, technical support period</p> <p>Regulatory: conformance to regulations, standards, and codes</p> <p>Other: reliability, availability, safety, expandability, documentation</p>

The level of detail depends much on the capabilities and efforts of the buyer, and there are many ways to proceed. In the very simplistic form, the buyer only provides a use-case definition or a coarse estimate of the duty cycle accompanied with some performance requirements such as ambient temperature and expected lifetime. In this case, the proposals are often difficult to evaluate and compare, because the requirements specification was so generic. As a result, the likelihood of buying a

system that does not perform well in the final application or is otherwise sub-optimal is high. To avoid the aforementioned pitfalls, the requirements specification shall be detailed enough so that the storage system suppliers can prepare binding proposals with sufficient performance and commensurable properties and conditions based on the requirements specification document. With a detailed requirements specification, it is more likely that the battery will perform well for the whole lifespan, and the proposals are easier to evaluate and compare.

The anticipated duty cycle of the battery is needed for determining the performance requirements. Therefore, the expected load power profiles and their occurrences should be determined for all anticipated applications. There are then two approaches how to proceed:

1. The buyer attaches these load profiles and use case descriptions into the RFP, and the battery system supplier performs a complete analysis and designs the whole system.
2. The buyer performs a detailed analysis of the mission profile, and based on the analysis, defines the performance requirements with a high level of detail.

The option #1 is easy for the buyer, but it might require a high effort for the supplier to provide a proposal. It easily leads to a conservative and expensive design too, as the supplier takes all the risks of the storage system not meeting the performance requirements. Consequently, this option is often possible only for sufficiently large storage procurements, because of high amount of work effort needed from the supplier's side.

The option #2 is easier for the battery supplier, as it is sufficient for them to design and offer a system that meets the detailed performance requirements defined by the buyer. However, it is way more demanding for the buyer to extract all the information, especially in cases where the buyer does not have expertise on battery technologies.

4.4 Tendering

Tendering can be executed in one or two stages. For small storages with clear requirement specification and wide product offering in the market, an RFP can be directly issued. For bigger and more complicated storage projects, a two-phase tendering consisting of a request for information (RFI) and an RFP is recommended [9]. In two-stage tendering, the RFI is first issued to collect information on the suppliers'

offering and capabilities and to obtain feedback for possible needs to fine tune the requirements specification and the RFP.

The documentation provided in the RFP shall include

- functional requirements
- non-functional requirements
- contractual obligations, liabilities, and remedies.

It is emphasized in [7] that even though grid-scale energy storage systems do not yet have a comprehensive standard addressing the certification of manufacturing of components, the conformity of assessment to ensure that the ESS complies with proper codes and standards should be carried out. Furthermore, a two-phase process is proposed, including factory acceptance testing (FAT) and a certification or listing inspecting subsequent production at the factory and reviews relevant documentation to claim that the product meets the test standards. The FAT is aimed at proving the system-scale performance and compliance with codes, standards, rules, and regulations applicable to the ESS project. Also site acceptance testing (SAT) should be specified in detail, as it marks an important milestone in the ESS project and concludes the installation process.

4.5 Decision-making

The obtained proposals are evaluated and ranked with all relevant criteria. The criteria and indicators depend on the goals and scopes of the project and use case. In multi-criteria decision-making, which is often used in the assessment of ESS projects, these criteria are typically distributed into four main categories; economic, environmental, technological, and social criteria [14]. A non-exhaustive list of criteria and indicators under these categories is shown in Table 2. The indicators for *cost*, *benefit*, *impact on CO₂ emissions*, and *performance criteria* are quantitative, and they can be calculated or predicted with specific tools. The rest of the criteria and indicators are more qualitative in nature. In addition to these categories, also the supplier assessment may have an impact on the decision-making.

Table 2: Storage selection decision-making: categories, criteria, and indicators.

ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	TECHNOLOGICAL	SOCIAL
Cost	Impact on CO₂ emissions	Performance	Security and reliability of energy provision
Capital expenditure	CO ₂ footprint ¹⁾	Energy capacity	Security of supply
Operating expenditure	CO ₂ handprint ²⁾	Discharging power capacity	Reliability
Cost/kWh	Sustainability of raw materials	Charging power capacity	Political stability and legitimacy
Cost/kWh	Recyclability	Response time	Potential of conflicts
Cost/kWh/cycle	Use of critical raw materials	Efficiency	Social and individual risks
Levelised cost of storage		Lifespan	Acceptance
Benefit		Safety	Trust
Avoided costs		Size and weight	Health concerns
Profits		Technology	Catastrophic potential
Residual value		Management systems	Familiarity with risks
		Communication & control systems	Quality of life
		Maturity & reliability	Impact on human health
		Compatibility with existing systems	Electricity costs
		Future proofness	Functional impact on landscape
		Product life cycle	Aesthetic impact on landscape
		Warranty	Job opportunities
		Technical support / service	
		Delivery time & commissioning	
		Expandability	
		Sourcing	
		Recycling	
		Possibility for repurposing	

Stationary grid storage applications are very cost-sensitive, and therefore, the economical indicators often play a very important role in the decision-making. It is also often found advantageous to work with a local supplier or system integrator, who can provide local technical support and knows the local regulations and authorities.

The LCOS calculation procedure is not defined in any international standard, but it is commonly used in energy storage projects. There are several slightly different definitions, but in general, the LCOS is determined as the sum of all the investment and operating costs during the whole lifetime of the storage divided by the total delivered energy. It provides a simple €/kWh metric of the costs that result in zero net present value. The LCOS takes into account the investment cost, the operating and maintenance cost, the energy cost caused by the roundtrip energy losses and charging of the storage, the costs incurred by the end-of-life treatment such as recycling costs, and the inflation and discount rates.

5 Technical and environmental considerations

5.1 Safety

Lithium-ion batteries must operate within a safe and reliable operating area, which is restricted by the voltage and temperature. Violation of these voltage and temperature windows leads to accelerated performance degradation as well as to increased safety

risk levels and even hazards. Batteries are always energized, even when disconnected from the rest of the system. An uncontrolled release of the potential energy can cause battery fire. Furthermore, once a cell catches fire, the fire propagates easily to adjacent cells, and consequently, the whole battery pack and storage system might end up in fire.

Hazards associated with lithium-ion cells can originate from high temperature or internal short circuit, which leads to rapid overheating. These events are typically a consequence of a former violation of the safe voltage or temperature window. For batteries with graphite-based anodes, the main safety issues and their origins are explained briefly below [15]:

- **Overdischarge:** If the cut-off voltage is exceeded, the copper in the current collector of the anode dissolves into the electrolyte. If the battery is then recharged, the dissolved copper forms metallic dendrites on the anode, which may puncture the separator and cause a short circuit. An extremely low voltage may additionally lead to the reduction of the electrolyte and production of gas.
- **Overcharge:** Exceeding the maximum voltage will lead to the decomposition of the cathode, which will produce high amounts of heat, and hence, rapid heating. It will also lead to the deposition of metallic lithium in the surface of the anode, which will increase the risk of internal short circuit. Extremely high voltage will also lead to the decomposition of the electrolyte.
- **Low temperature:** Charging at subzero temperature leads to the deposition of metallic lithium on the surface of the anode, and therefore, reduces the cycle life. At an extremely low temperature, the cathode will break down, which results in an internal short circuit.
- **High temperature:** The solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) film will start an exothermic decomposition typically at around 100 °C temperature. When the temperature exceeds 120 °C, the SEI film cannot anymore protect the anode from side reactions with the organic electrolyte, and combustible gas is produced. After 130 °C temperature, the separator starts to melt and shuts the cell down. When the temperature becomes higher, the cathode starts to decompose, which releases oxygen and produces high amounts of heat. The temperature threshold for the decomposition varies with the cathode composition. At around 200 °C, the electrolyte starts to decompose and produce combustible gas, which reacts with the oxygen from the decomposed cathode. This is a high-rate exothermic process with temperature increase rates

as high as 100 °C/min. Eventually, the cell starts to catch fire and a thermal runaway is initiated.

For batteries with LTO anode, overdischarging does not result in the formation of metallic dendrites, because LTO batteries use aluminum current collector in the anode as well. Also charging at subzero temperature is allowed.

Hazards associated with lithium-ion battery packs may originate from a short circuit within the cells or from external sources such as short circuits between cells, busbars, and other metallic components, failures in the control circuitry of the battery, or hot spots in the electric connectors. These external failures heat the battery cells either internally due to high current or externally due to a nearby hot spot. Therefore, safety risks shall be controlled and mitigated at all levels. Table 3 lists safety aspects that contribute into the total safety and mitigation of risks at each system level.

Table 3: Safety aspects at different system levels.

Cell	Module/pack/system	System management	Infrastructure
Technology selection	Electrical design	Supervisory control and data acquisition	Location of the battery installation
	Thermal design		
	Mechanical design	Load control	Fire suppression system
	Current interrupting devices	Battery disconnect	
	Battery management system		

5.2 Ageing and performance degradation

The performance of lithium-ion batteries gradually deteriorates as a function of usage and calendar age. The degradation of lithium-ion battery is a complex combination of electrochemical and mechanical processes, which lead to decrease in battery capacity and increase in battery impedance. Consequently, battery degradation leads to its reduced ability to store energy and provide power. The degree of battery ageing is described with battery state of health (SOH).

The rate of LIB degradation is significantly influenced by several operating practices and environmental conditions. These factors are called degradation stress factors. The main degradation stress factors during usage are the depth of the charge–discharge cycles, average state of charge (SOC) during cycling, operating temperature, and the magnitude of the charge and discharge current. During idle time the main degradation stress factors are the SOC and the environmental temperature. The degradation stress factors and the corresponding high stress conditions for typical LIBs are presented in

Table 4. The effect of different stress factors varies among different LIB chemistries, but the general trend is the same. By avoiding high stress conditions, the degradation can be reduced and the lifetime can be improved. Degradation stress factor characteristics for different LIB technologies gathered from the scientific literature can be found from [6].

Table 4: Degradation stress factors and corresponding high stress conditions.

Category	Stress factor	High stress condition
Cycle ageing	DOD	High DOD
	Average SOC	Low or high average SOC
	Temperature	Low or high temperature
	Current	High current
Calendar ageing	SOC	High SOC
	Temperature	High temperature

5.3 Battery system integration

Battery cells have only a very limited voltage, power, and energy ratings, and therefore, multiple cells need to be connected in series and parallel to achieve the voltage, power, and energy needs of the target application. For practical reasons, especially to avoid excessive weight of a single unit and to achieve modularity and easy scalability, the cells are first packed to battery modules. Then, a battery pack is formed by connecting multiple modules in series and/or parallel. In large systems, the total battery system may consist of multiple parallel-connected battery packs, which are also often called as battery strings.

5.3.1 Module and pack assembly

Battery cells are typically assembled in a module, which includes multiple cells with proper mounting, interconnections, cell-voltage measurements, temperature measurements, enclosure, and terminals. A module may also include other systems such as active or passive cooling, heating, fuses, current measurement, and cell-equalization electronics. Battery modules typically have 3–20 cells connected in series. Parallel connections of two or more cells are also common, giving more flexibility to battery designs.

A battery pack consists of multiple battery modules, internal connections, external connections, and an enclosure. In addition, it typically has at least a battery management system (BMS), a thermal management system, contactors, fuses, and a

precharge circuit. It may also have, e.g., an isolation monitoring device and additional sensors.

5.3.2 Battery management system

The use of a BMS is important to manage battery modules and packs. Without a BMS the battery will eventually become unbalanced, because the cells have different leakage currents that discharge the cells slowly with different rates. A BMS is also needed to estimate the battery's state and condition, such as the SOC and SOH, as well as to provide advanced mechanisms to protect the battery from hazardous and inefficient operating conditions such as overtemperature, undertemperature, overvoltage, and undervoltage. Hence, the tasks of a BMS can be divided into three categories:

- Safety-related tasks such as preventing overcurrent, overcharging, and overdischarging from happening by controlling the battery current directly or indirectly.
- Optimization-related tasks such as cell balancing and current limiting at low and high temperatures and SOCs, which maximize the performance and lifetime of the battery.
- Monitoring and prediction of properties such as current, voltage, temperature, SOC, SOH, available energy, and available power to provide information to the vehicle control unit.

The BMS must be configured and calibrated carefully for the dedicated system. Otherwise, the safety features and state estimation algorithms do not operate properly. Battery system integrators are responsible for the selection, configuration, and calibration of the BMS.

5.3.3 Thermal management

Thermal management is very important in lithium-ion battery systems due to safety concerns and higher degradation rate at high and low temperatures. The battery generates heat during loading, and the heat must be effectively dissipated into ambient air or coolant to keep the operating temperature within the desired range. The optimal operating temperature range of batteries is approximately 15–35 °C. In this range the efficiency, lifetime, and performance are good, and there are no temperature-related safety risks. The efficiency and performance get even better at higher temperatures, but, adversely, the battery also degrades at a higher rate. The upper limit for the

temperature is typically set in the vicinity of 50 °C. At this temperature, the calendar life and the cycle life are drastically shortened. There is, however, still a wide safety margin before exothermic reactions begin to happen, which could result in an uncontrolled heating and a thermal runaway. At operating temperatures lower than 15 °C, the usable energy and power capability are decreased, the efficiency is decreased, and the degradation rate is increased. Therefore, the performance is often derated at low temperatures. At subzero operating temperatures, charging is typically not allowed, and discharging is allowed only at very low current rate. However, due to significantly higher impedance at very low temperatures, the battery will self-heat effectively during discharging at a low rate.

5.3.4 Protection devices

Typical protection systems include fuses or circuit breakers for short-circuit protection, contactors or other main switches for disconnecting the battery from the system, and isolation monitoring device for detecting ground faults and degradation of electrical isolation. In large battery systems, also a fire protection system and an exhaust gas manifold are often used.

5.3.5 Grid storages

Grid storages are typically formed by assembling battery modules into vertical racks. The size of the storage can be scaled by combining several racks. Depending on the total capacity of the storage and the customer's preference, the racks are typically installed inside a cabinet or a container. Containerized storages typically include the whole energy storage system from battery modules to supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) and control systems as well as interfacing power electronics converters, thermal management system, and protection devices.

5.4 Second-life batteries

Extending the life of EV batteries by collecting and repurposing the batteries in second-life applications provides a promising way to reduce the environmental impacts of EVs as well as to reduce the cost of storage in stationary applications. Many stationary grid applications are seen as potential applications for second-life EV batteries. However, the development of second life applications of used LIBs is still a very new market, because most of the EV batteries are still in the early phase of their life. It will still take years before these batteries reach their end of life (EOL) and are ready for either

recycling or being prepared for second life applications. Moreover, the main challenges related to the access to the data regarding the battery health and usage history needs to be solved to enable cost-effective business. Due to lack of supply of batteries for refurbishment, the cost is still high. On the other hand, also very low prices are reported already now; according to Capgemini [16], the cost of second-life repurposed battery is around 50 \$/kWh. It is forecasted that by 2030 repurposed EV second-life batteries will replace 20 GWh of annual ESS installations, representing 6% of that year's global demand for stationary battery storage [17].

Second-life batteries have lower performance than first-life batteries due to their lower capacity and higher impedance. Nevertheless, stationary grid storage applications are very cost-driven, and therefore, second-life batteries are attractive for many use cases. There are several downsides, though, that need to be taken into account in the decision-making regarding second-life batteries:

- Lifetime is much shorter compared to a new battery
- There is a risk of higher rate of degradation than expected or a major increase in the rate of degradation at some point of life
- Warranty is typically much shorter compared to a new battery
- Efficiency is lower compared to a new battery
- There is a risk of lower reliability
- There is a risk of lower safety characteristics
- There is an increased risk of hazards related to internal faults such as internal short circuit

5.5 Life cycle assessment

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a systematic and standardized method to analyze the environmental impact of a product during its whole life cycle from raw material extraction to final disposal or recycling. The environmental impact can be determined by a number of factors such as climate change impact (carbon footprint), ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, or fresh water eutrophication.

A typical LCA study includes four stages: (i) goal and scope definition, (ii) life cycle inventory (LCI), (iii) life cycle impact assessment (LCIA), and (iv) life cycle interpretation. When applying the LCA method to batteries, the goal could be to quantify the climate change impacts of production, use, and disposal or recycling of the

battery. In other words, calculating the carbon footprint of the battery covering its whole life cycle. In LCA, the scope definition plays a key role. , e.g., shall only the battery modules taken into account in calculating the environmental impact, or shall other components such as power electronics or thermal management system also be included? An essential step in LCA is the life cycle inventory stage, which contains the collection of data from all stages of the product's life cycle. Data related to the environmental impact of the product is collected from databases, such as Ecoinvent Database [18], from scientific literature, or from primary sources, if possible. In the life cycle impact assessment step, the significance of the environmental impacts is evaluated based on the results of the previous step. Finally, in the life cycle interpretation step, the results are systematically summarized and recommendations to reduce the environmental impacts of the product during its life cycle can be made. For example, extending the battery's lifetime by avoiding the conditions that accelerate its degradation reduces the actual environmental impact of the battery.

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